

Factors Hindering Teachers Of English Language From Implementing Communicative Language Teaching (Clt) Approach: A Case Of Selected Secondary Schools In Kasama District, Zambia

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Abstract- English Language teaching has undergone noticeable pedagogical changes over time. From the late 1960s hitherto, Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) Approach has been adopted for use in the syllabi of English as Foreign Language (EFL) as well as English as Second Language (ESL) contexts. The study explored the implementation of CLT in Public Secondary Schools of kasama District. The purpose of the study was to establish why teachers of English Language were not implementing CLT. Mixed Method Approach was used and a case study in this regard applied. The findings of the study from the first objective, which aimed at assessing teachers' understanding of CLT revealed that teachers had scanty ideas that CLT aims at making learners attain communicative competence even though, all the forty-one (100%) teachers under study could not give a comprehensive theoretical account of CLT. The study also showed that thirty-one (75.6%) teachers held misconceptions while ten (24.4) could not state what CLT was. The findings of the second objectives, which aimed at exploring the extent to which CLT was absent in English Language lessons showed that CLT to a large extent was absent in all the lessons observed. Structural lessons dominated and these were explicitly taught outside meaningful language tasks. All the lessons were organized around teacher centered whole class pedagogical activities without any noticeable form of communicative activities and CLT instructional procedures. The study also showed that the text based course books used in the schools under study to teach English Language were pedagogical in nature and no authentic materials were used in all the lessons observed. The findings of the last objective, which intended to establish the factors hindering teachers from implementing CLT revealed factors such as inadequate pre-service training, insufficient funding to support CLT, large classes, negative attitude of the teacher toward CLT, from-based examinations and pupils' low English proficiency to be among other factors hindering teachers from implementing CLT. The study provided a range of practical recommendations that included among others the need for the trainers of teachers of English Language to be practical and not theoretical in their training.

Keywords- Communicative, Language, Teaching

I. Introduction

This chapter presents background information to the study, the statement of the problem and purpose of the study. Research objectives and questions are also stated accordingly. The chapter further discusses the significance of the study, limitations and delimitation of the study. Finally, definitions to operational terms are also given.

II. Background to the Study

Language teaching is a dynamic field of education where a cluster of changes has been suggested and implemented over time (Whong, 2011). These changes in teaching approaches and methods throughout history stem from a demand for the most suitable approaches for language teaching.

At any given moment in the past, when linguists and teachers realized that particular theories of language and language learning were not meeting the needs of a society, they initiated a search for a new approach which would solve the problem (Howatt, 1984; Richards & Rodgers, 1986).

During the first half of the twentieth century, the teaching of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) emerged as an autonomous profession. In the course of time, it spawned further distinct specialisms, notably the teaching of English as a Second Language (ESL), at first in the Empire, later the commonwealth, and more recently in Britain itself. The second strand in the development of English Language Teaching (ELT) in the modern sense was derived from the reinterpretation of the role of English in the Empire. During the nineteenth century, there was a largely unquestioned assumption that English should be taught in the colonial schools in essentially the same way as in Britain.

The basic assumption was the assimilation of British culture through the medium of English Literature. There was no provision for language work specifically designed to help the non-native learners. Local examinations were exported in large numbers to the colonies. By the twenties, the notion that English was a second language with a utilitarian function in the communication of knowledge had begun to emerge, though it was not until the fifties that the modern distinction between English as a foreign and a second language became widespread. In broader terms, the twenties were a period of research, the thirties of development (Howatt, 1984).

The English language teaching development introduced different innovation in terms of methods and approaches. The earliest was the Grammar Translation Method which was in vogue up to 1940s. Its genesis was a result of a shift from the use of classics to the vernacular, English included (Richards & Rodgers, 1986; Whong, 2011). This method achieved limited success. The type of Grammar Translation Courses was disliked by thousands of school learners, for whom foreign language learning meant a tedious experience of memorizing endless lists of un usable grammar rules and vocabulary and attempting to produce perfect translation of silted and literary prose (Howatt, 1984).

CLT has not only developed out of linguistic concerns but also as a result of a broader trend in education as well. Progressivism in mainstream education emphasizes the needs of students as individual; it promotes the idea that active learning through doing and discovery is more effective than the passive absorption of bodies of knowledge (Whong, 2011).

Statement Of The Problem

The Zambia English Language Syllabi for Secondary Schools states that teachers of English Language use CLT in their teaching so as to enable the learners develop communicative competence (MESVTEE, 2013). However, results from studies on countries where CLT has been adopted, such as Taiwan, Republic of South Africa, Zimbabwe, New Zealand and indeed in Zambia showed that teachers were not implementing CLT (Chang, 2010; Weimann, 1996; Mareva & Nyota, 2011; Vongxay, 2013 and Munakaampe, 2005). Using kasama District Public Secondary Schools as a case study, the researcher wanted to establish why teachers were not implementing CLT. Stated as a question, the research problem was ‘What are the factors hindering teachers of English Language in kasama District Public Secondary Schools from implementing CLT Approach?’

The Objectives Of The Study

1. Assess the teachers’ understanding of CLT.
2. Explore the extent of the absence of CLT in English Language Lessons.
3. Establish the factors hindering the teachers from implementing CLT.

Significance Of The Study

The findings of the study may enlighten the teachers on the pedagogical requirements of the English Language Syllabi and sensitize trainers of English Language teachers on the need to be practical and not theoretical as far as training in CLT is concerned. The ministry of General Education may also be helped to understand the complexity of introducing CLT so that it gets more focused and efficient in monitoring as well as allocation of resources to schools. Finally, the findings of the study will contribute to the body of knowledge on CLT.

III. Literature Review

Literature review according to Kombo and Tromp (2006, 62) is “an account of what has been published on a topic by accredited scholars and researchers.” It involves a critical analysis of documents such as books, magazines, journals, dissertations and newspaper reports. Literature review provides the researcher with a degree of competence within his research area, assists in developing the researcher’s knowledge, and identifies the boundaries of previous research therefore, focusing and justifying the research problem (Ng’andu, 2013). This chapter reviews relevant literature.

Communicate Language Teaching (CLT) Approach

CLT Approach is derived from a multidisciplinary perspective that includes, at least, Linguistics, Psychology, Philosophy, Sociology and Educational Research (Savignon, 1991). It is a recent and widely used hybrid approach to language teaching, essentially viewed as progressive rather than traditional. It has no single authority or text on it, or any single model that is universally acceptable as authoritative (Richards and Rodgers, 1986). However, Howatt (1984) distinguishes between a ‘strong’ and a ‘weak’ version of CLT. The weak version stresses the importance of providing learners with opportunities to use their English for communicative purposes and,

characteristically, attempts to integrate such activities into a wider programme of language teaching. The 'stronger' version of communicative teaching, on the other hand, advances the claim that language is acquired through communication so that it is not merely a question of activating an existing but inert knowledge of language, but of stimulating the development of the language system itself. The former could be described as "learning to use English; the latter entails using English to learn it" (Howatt, 1984; 279).

Communicative Competence

The notion of 'communicative competence' was proposed to counter Chomsky's competence/performance distinctions. For Chomsky, the focus of linguistic theory was to characterize the abstract abilities speakers possess that enable them produce grammatically correct sentences in a language (Richards & Rodgers, 1986). Such a view according to Hymes (1972) was sterile and argues that linguistic theory needed to be seen as part of a more general theory incorporating communication and culture. Hymes's (1972) theory of communicative competence refers to the knowledge and abilities required for a speaker to be able to participate successfully in a speech community (Whong, 2011). In Hymes view, a person who acquires communicative competence acquires both knowledge and ability for language use with respect to whether something is formally possible, feasible and appropriate and is in fact done or performed (Hymes, 1972).

Hymes's(1972) communicative competence view is complemented by Halliday's elaborate theory of the functions of language which is favoured in CLT. Halliday describes seven (7) basic functions that language performs for children learning their first Language (Richards & Rodgers, 1986). These are the instrumental, regulatory, interactional, personal, heuristic, imaginative and representational functions. These functions can be interpreted as; using language to get things done, control the behaviour of others, create interaction with others, express personal feelings and meanings, learn and discover, create a world of the imagination and finally using language to communicate information respectively (Richards & Rodgers, 1986).

Another theorist frequently cited for his views on the communicative nature of language is Henry Widdowson (1978). His view focuses on the communicative acts underlying the ability to use language for different purposes. He represents a view of the relationship between linguistic system and their communicative values in text and discourse.

A more recent but related analysis of communicative competence is found in Canale and Swain (1980), in which four dimensions of communicative competence are identified as grammatical, sociolinguistics, discourse and strategic competences. To begin with, Canale and Swain (1980) acknowledged that grammatical or linguistic competence is an essential part of being communicatively competent. This type of competence includes the linguistic forms which are traditionally subsumed under the category of grammar, including rules of sentence structure, word formation and pronunciation. The second dimension is sociolinguistics or pragmatic competence which refers to an "understanding of the social context in which communication takes place, including role relationship, the shared information of the participants, and the

communicative purpose for their interaction” (Richards & Rodgers, 1986; 71). Discourse competence is understood in terms of the interaction of individual message elements in terms of their interconnectedness and of how meaning is represented in relationship to the entire discourse or text. Lastly, they proposed strategic competence which basically refers to the coping strategies that are employed by communicators to initiate, terminate, maintain, repair, and redirect communication (Richards & Rodgers, 2001).

Bachman (1990) appends strategic competence as a completely separate element of communication language ability, which essentially serves an executive function of making the final decision, among all possible alternatives, on wording, phrasing, and other means for negotiating meaning. From the foregoing discussion, it is clear that CLT has rich, eclectic theoretical base but very little has been written about the learning theories. Nevertheless, elements of an underlying learning theory can be discerned in some CLT practices. Some of the practices as suggested by Richards & Rodgers (1986) include: Communicative principle, task principle and meaningfulness principle. Suffice to state that more recent accounts of CLT have attempted to describe theories of language learning processes that are compatible with the CLT Approach. Among other theorists include Savignon (1983), Krashen (1981) and Johnson (1984).

Principles and Characteristics of CLT

Arising from the language and learning theories, CLT adheres to a range of principles which in turn give rise to particular teaching methods and ultimately teaching techniques. As afore stated, CLT gives primary attention to function of the language and secondary importance to structural aspect of language. The functional view sees language as a system for expressing meaning and thus the primary purpose of language is to facilitate interaction and communication (Littlewood, 1981). Meaning in this regard is paramount than the traditional focus on grammar rules (Richards & Rodgers, 1986). Widdowson (1978) refers to it as ‘value,’ as opposed to dictionary meaning which he refers to as ‘signification’.

Functionalists are not necessarily dismissive of structure forms but see forms as a realisation of function. The interest is in exploring the mapping from function to form. Many problems with or questions about language forms or structure should be addressed as they arise. If they are explicitly introduced by the teacher, this should not be done outside meaningful language tasks. Attention to form will occur if there is a breakdown in communication or if a learner is unclear about some points of language (Whong, 2011).

Fluency and accuracy are seen as complementary principles underlying communicative techniques (Brown, 1994). However, at times fluency may have to take more importance than accuracy because fluency and acceptable language is the primary goal: accuracy is judged not in the abstract but in context (Richards & Rodgers, 1986). Fluency is emphasized over accuracy in order to keep learners meaningfully engaged in language use. Learners are therefore, encouraged to speak without worrying too much about correct forms as long as communication is successful. This does not mean that errors are entirely ignored, but they are often seen

as secondary to the more important aim of maximizing language production. This can also apply to written forms. CLT teachers should comment on the ideas and/or overall message of writing. The extent to which they comment on the grammar, vocabulary and spellings is likely to vary unless these errors lead to an inability to make sense of the written message. This is supported by a view that sees language development as occurring in natural settings, as it may be more useful to overlook errors which signal a level of development yet to be achieved (Whong, 2011).

Language teaching techniques in CLT are designed to engage learners in the pragmatic, authentic, functional use of language for meaningful purposes. CLT classrooms should provide opportunities for the use of real situations that necessitate communication. The situations should mirror the real life; it must be authentic in terms of being realistic as opposed to being contrived purely for teaching purposes (Widdowson, 1984). Creative role plays, simulations, dramas, games, project stimulate real situations. Classroom activities should be designed to focus on completing tasks that are mediated through language or involve negotiation of information and information sharing (Richards & Rodgers, 1986). Similarly, CLT use authentic materials taken from non-pedagogic sources; realia such as magazines, brochures and real videos or audio broadcasts (Whong, 2011). It is felt desirable in CLT to give students the opportunities to develop strategies for understanding language as it is actually used by native speakers.

CLT is in support of collaborative learning. Cooperative Learning requires learners to work together for greater improvement in individual learning and allows learners to learn from each other (Whong, 2011). This interaction can either be in the flesh through group and pair work or in their writings (Richards & Rodgers, 1986). CLT is in this regard, a learner centered and experience based approach. It promotes learner autonomy; language learning users should take ownership of their language development instead of relying heavily on the teacher or the classroom materials. This is compatible with the idea of reflective learning which is associated with techniques such as the use of learner diary, journal or blog, in which learners are asked to record their thoughts and observations about the process of learning as they experience it (Whong, 2011; Richards & Rodgers, 1986). The roles of the teacher in this regard are that of an organiser, a guide within the classroom procedures and activities and also a researcher and learner. The teacher also assumes the roles of a need analyst, counselor and group process manager (Richards & Rodgers, 1986).

CLT is also compatible with a socio-cultural view which sees language as tied to cultural practices and contexts. In order to promote a connection between language and culture, a CLT classroom can try to create the atmosphere of the culture the target language is spoken. This can be done physically with cultural artifacts such as pictures, photos, magazines, books and music. Of course any attempt to create a genuine target language atmosphere requires the (exclusive) use of the target language by the teacher, not only during formal instruction but also in the formal interactions that take place, as well as an insistence that learners use only the target language while in class. This will maximize the amount of natural input that learners receive in class (Whong, 2011). CLT is also characterized by an integrated skills approach

whereby a single activity or set of activities in a CLT classroom is likely to make use of the four skills: speaking, listening, reading and writing (Whong, 2011).

Teachers' Understanding of CLT and the Extent of its Implementation

There are several studies that have been conducted to assess teachers' understanding of CLT. Among other studies is the study by Vongxay (2013) who conducted a qualitative research to explore the understandings and attitudes of English teachers in Lao Higher Educational Institution in New Zealand. According to his report, most of the interviewees appeared to have a superficial understanding of CLT. For them, CLT meant an interaction among students in the classroom activities while teachers acted as facilitators, assistants and consultants who guide students. These teachers also reported that communication activities only refer to speaking and listening tasks and none of them mentioned that communicative activities could be in forms of writing, reading as well as the involvement of sentence structure which was the key element of communicative competence.

Another study by Singh and Li (2005) found that most teachers and students in an English-major college in China reported that CLT means teaching only speaking and listening without grammatical competence. As a result, both teachers and students in their research put the stress on speaking and listening skills. In relation to this, Sato and Kleinsasser (1999) conducted the research on the views and practices of CLT by Japanese Second Language in-service teachers. These teachers reported that for them CLT means group work and pair work that only related to speaking. Most of the teachers in the study understood that there was no grammar involved in communicative activities while some teachers in this research project did not directly mention grammar usage in the communicative activities. To support this result, Li (1998) also found that Korean Secondary School English Teachers defined communicative activities as group work and pair work which only focused on speaking and there was no grammar involvement. These findings are also similar to Gamal and Debra (2001) findings that Egyptian teachers perceived communicative tasks as speaking activities. The teachers did not refer to the involvement of sentence structure which is also one of the key elements of communicative competence.

Another remarkable study on secondary school teachers' conception of CLT in ESL context was done by Mareva and Mapako (2012). The focus of the study was on how CLT is conceptualised by secondary school teachers in Masvingo District in Zimbabwe. They employed qualitative research design and data was collected through in depth interview with the 24 purposively sampled secondary school teachers. The study established among other things that CLT was understood to focus on communicative competence where interactive techniques such as pair work, group work, role play and games are used in the CLT classroom. Teachers conceptualised it as a paradigm that foregrounds meaning and contextualised teaching where a wide variety of learning aids that instigate and sustain communication are used. The interviewees also showed an awareness of CLT as a learner-centred approach where the student is expected to take centre stage in the learning process. The researchers however, unearthed eleven misconceptions which suggested that the implementation of CLT in secondary schools in Zimbabwe remain controversial. Among these misconceptions include the understanding that CLT implies that teachers abdicate

their roles since the approach is learner-centred. The researchers also stated that the respondents said that the approach encourages the abandonment of teaching grammar and placed emphasis on the skills of speaking and listening.

Similarly, Vongxay (2013) study revealed a partial implementation of CLT. All the teachers in the study reported that the department's syllabus was based on grammatical linguistics rather than other skills like speaking, reading and writing. On the other hand, listening and oral communication subjects were removed from the department's syllabus. Due to the syllabus, there was more focus on grammatical knowledge than the other skills and both teachers and students definitely had to concentrate on sentence structure. Not only did the syllabus emphasis grammar, but teachers in this study also persevered in using grammar-based teaching approach in classes rather than the recently introduced CLT into their classroom teaching. Only 30% of CLT was applied into their classroom while 70% was still teacher centred.

In another study, Weimann (1996) revealed that CLT was absent from the classroom in Ciskeian secondary schools in the Republic of South Africa. In all the classrooms observed, most activities were organised in terms of a teacher-student/ class format focusing on teacher-led, whole-class activities. Supporting a transmission mode of teaching in which little opportunity is provided for 'natural communication' in the classroom. Students are not afforded opportunities for initiating discourse and thus play no role in the negotiation and creating of learning opportunities. Students are offered few opportunities for practicing language skills in an integrated, whole-language manner using sustained speech. The classroom interaction perpetuated the exchange of information which was predicted and artificial. Classroom practice utilised materials that were pedagogic in nature and thus did not exemplify the type of language material that students were likely to encounter in 'real-world' language environment.

The fact that CLT calls for real life communication during English lessons cannot be over emphasized. It is however, not clear what variables the research used to measure the presence or absence of real life communication because a critical examination of the instruments used does not convincingly bring out this aspect. The instruments for lack of a better term were not comprehensive enough taking into account the complexity of CLT. It is therefore, expected in this research that variables from COLT protocol are used when designing the instruments so that CLT can be comprehensively examined in the lessons. The researcher also looked at CLT at primary level, Grade Five to be specific. This study changes the focus as it looks at CLT at secondary school level because teachers at this level specialise in particular subjects and it is therefore, expected that more time is probably spent on pedagogy.

Gross et. al (1971), gives a different view on why teachers display a negative attitude towards innovations. They contend that a major reason for the failure of the innovation was the initial resistance on the part of those closely involved with the institution or system within which the innovation was being implemented. He argues that participants in the change process are largely dependent upon their formal leaders to overcome such obstacles but the required help might not materialise. Equally,

members who were initially supportive of such change develop a negative attitude as a direct result of the frustrations they encountered in their attempt to carry it out.

Closely related to the above issue, is the lack of English language proficiency by teachers which has been cited as one of the factors negatively affecting the implementation of CLT. Ellis (1996) argues that the successful adoption of CLT into English Languages classrooms depends on among other things, the English Language proficiency of the teachers. Most teachers of English Language have been reported to lack the ability to teach communicatively and this affect their teaching of CLT (Hird, 1995). Similarly, Li (1998) observed in his study that Chinese teachers' abilities in English skills of reading and writing were inadequate to enable them conduct communicative activities in their classes. Similar findings were recorded by Weimann (1996) in Ciskeian Secondary Schools.

By and large, it would be of great interest to investigate if teachers of English in Zambia are also affected in this area especially that unlike Asian States, Zambians hitherto have used English as a medium of instruction from the initial grades to tertiary education (MOE, 1996). Would we safely say that Zambian teachers of English Language have high levels of proficiency in English Language? The research in question attended to such concerns.

Factors Attributed to Pupils

Pupils also play a vital role in the successful implementation of CLT. To begin with, CLT offers more interaction among students through co-operative learning (Whong, 2011). However, tradition and culture has been reported by researchers to have a bearing on the successful implementation of CLT in certain instances. Bower and Prodromou (1992) observed that there has been increasing interest in recent years in the relationship between language learning and cross-cultural awareness within the field of English language teaching.

The methods and approaches demanded by innovation, for example, are often in conflict with the practitioners own cultural background. Any methodology, such as that under the banner of CLT, which incorporates aspects of pupil centered approach, is likely to clash in practice with traditional values. Because the educational practices of a country or a people are so deeply rooted in its culture and its underlying pre-suppositions, the dominance of the learner's culture, and for that matter, the dominance of the teacher's culture is a factor that needs to be reckoned with when thinking about ESL in general, and about innovation such as CLT, in particular (Alptekin, 1982).

Factors Attributed to the Education System

A study on English teachers' perception in adopting CLT approach in Korea recommended that South Korea needed to change the fundamental approach to education because the predominance of text centered and grammar-centered practices in Korea did not provide the basis for the student centered, fluency-focused, and problem solving activities required by CLT (Li, 1998). A study on Ciskeian Secondary Schools also reported structural tests and examinations to be a hindrance in implementing CLT. Taiwan examinations were also reported to orient teaching in the

colleges studied. The respondents (teachers) observed that if the examinations included communicative question in addition to grammar, it would naturally lead the teachers to teach in a communicative way. The teachers would focus on CLT if listening and speaking test items were included in their examinations. (Weimann, 1996; Chang, 2010).

Factors Attributed to the Environment

Social interaction is another key element for learning CLT. Lack of English speaking environment is yet another factor identified to be a cause of the poor implementation of CLT by the respondents. The reports, most of which are from EFL countries reviewed that there was a lack of supportive learning environment outside classrooms for CLT practice. The only place the students could use English was a classroom which in many cases did not offer ample time for students to practice the use of English language in meaningful contexts (Vongxay, 2013). The respondents further stated that not only was there no wider English usage outside class but also that the school never created an English environment by organising any events or competitions that would call for the use of English Language.

The studies reviewed in this chapter have demonstrated that CLT is not well understood by the teachers and it is not implemented in many counties where it has been adopted. The literature also reviewed that various factors hinder teachers from implementing CLT. However, much of literature reviewed was from EFL context as very little research has been done in ESL context, especially here in Zambia. The literature also reviewed gaps in terms of the methods and instruments employed by researchers. Above all, it was noted that no study holistically investigated the problem as Studies reviewed attended to isolated aspects of the problem. This research holistically studied the problem and filled up the gaps that were identified. The next chapter discusses the methodology used in this study.

IV. Methodology

Research Design

Research design is a scheme, plan or outline that is used to generate answers to research problems. (Orodho, 2003). In order to address different types of research questions, Mixed Method Approach was used. The combination of both qualitative and quantitative also provided an expanded understanding of research problems (Creswell, 2009). In this regard, Concurrent Triangulation Strategy was employed. The researcher collected both quantitative and qualitative data to determine if there is convergence, differences, or some combination.

This comparison is often referred to as confirmation, disconfirmation, Cross-validation, or corroboration (Creswell, 2009). The research also used a case study. A case study is “potentially the most valuable method known for obtaining a true and comprehensive picture of individuality” (Sidhu, 1984; 224). It explores in depth a programme, event, activity, process or one or more individuals (Creswell, 1992). The method was the most appropriate for the research because the researcher wanted to gain an in depth understanding of the factors hindering teachers of English Language from implementing CLT.

Target Population

“A population is any group of individuals that have one or more characteristics in common that are of interest to the researcher.” (Sidhu, 1984). It is from the population that the sample for study is taken. The population for this study comprised all teachers of English Language in Kasama District of Lusaka province.

Sample Size

A sample is basically a smaller group of a target population selected for inclusion in a study (Schulze, 2002). By observing the characteristics of the sample, one can make certain inferences about the characteristics of the population from which it is drawn. The sample consisted of 41 participants, all of them teachers of English Language drawn from the six public secondary schools in Kasama District.

The table shows that 37 (90.2%) respondents in the study were drawn from government schools while 4(9.8%) came from a grant aided school. In terms of gender, 11 males (26.8%) and 30 females (73.2%) participated in the study. More respondents were in the age range of 24-41. In terms of qualifications, the table shows that 22 (53.7%) were degree holders, 17 (41.5%) were diploma holders and 2 (4.9%) were master’s degree holders. Among the respondents 25 (61.0%) taught Senior Secondary while 16 (39.0%) taught Junior Secondary. Of the 41 respondents, 6(14.6%) were heads of departments, 8 (19.5%) were heads of sections and 27 (65.9%) were mere classroom teachers.

Data Collection Procedure

Data Collection Procedure explains how the data were collected. It includes measuring instruments, details of implementation for any intervention (e.g. length of treatment, time of day) and difference of conditions in treatment groups (If they are multiple groups) (Bui, 2009). As earlier stated, the data for this research were collected through questionnaires, observations and interviews. The questionnaires were distributed to all the 41 teachers of English Language in the six public Secondary Schools of Kasama District. Enough time for scoring was given to the respondents after which the researcher collected the questionnaires.

From each school, two lessons were observed randomly and that gives a total of 12 lessons that were observed. The observations were conducted in the classroom under natural, non-manipulative setting using an observation checklist. The researcher was a non-participant observer and sat at the back of the room to avoid any interference to the setting. The observed lessons lasted between forty to eighty minutes each and the whole exercise took one month. The observation sheet was used to code the classroom activities of each lesson. The lessons were also audio-recorded to provide a means of triangulation and thus confirm the coding done during the lessons.

The interviews with the teachers were conducted at the end of the classroom observation phase and after all the questionnaires were scored. Face to face interviews with the forty one teachers was conducted. Each of the interviews lasted between forty to fifty minutes and was conducted during each participant’s free time. The interview was tape recorded for accuracy. The interview added to the in-depth description and understanding of the practices observed in the respective classrooms.

Data Analysis

Data Analysis is a process of examining what has been collected in a research and making deductions and inferences. “It involves uncovering underlying structures, extracting important variables, detecting any anomalies and testing any underlying assumptions” (Kombo & Tromp, 2006; 117). The research employed Mixed Study method and therefore, data analysis occurred both within the qualitative and quantitative approach.

For qualitative data, the researcher used a linear, hierarchical approach of data analysis; building from the bottom to the top (Creswell, 2009). The data was first organised and prepared for analysis. This involved transcribing recorded interviews, and sorting and arranging the data into different types according to the sources of information. The researcher then read through the data to obtain a general sense of information and to reflect its overall meaning. Data was further analysed with a coding process that generated a small number of themes or categories. These themes were further analysed and the major theories were drawn out.

For quantitative data, the data was analysed using descriptive statistics. Descriptive statistics refers to “a set of concepts and methods used in organizing, summarizing, tabulating, depicting and describing collections of data” (Shavelson, 1996; 8). Researchers use this type of statistical analysis to describe the data set that was collected from the sample in a comprehensive and meaningful way. Individual scores, percentages, frequency counts are reported and presented using tables, charts and in figures as a graphical representation of the results to supplement the narrative explanation. Statistical analysis using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Software was used for much of the quantitative data.

This chapter has presented the methodology used in the research in terms of research design, target population, sample size, sampling procedure, research instruments, data collection procedure, data analysis and ethical issues considered. The next chapter presents the findings of the study.

V. Presentation Of Findings

Overview

The ultimate goal of any research is to respond to the questions and issues raised at the outset of the research initiative. In the case of this study, the questions raised were: ‘What is the teachers’ understanding of CLT?’ ‘To what extent is CLT absent in English Language Lessons?’ ‘What are the factors hindering teachers from implementing CLT?’ Thus, the presentation of findings is guided by the research questions.

To what extent is CLT absent in English Language Lessons?

Classroom Observation

A total number of twelve (12) lessons were observed from six (06) Secondary Schools under study. Of these lessons, six (06) were structure lessons, two (02) comprehension, two (02) summary lessons and the other two (02) were composition lessons. Of the structure lessons observed, two lessons were based on the topic

'Contrast' taught to two different Grade Ten classes from two different schools. The structure topic 'Conditional Sentences' and 'Question Tags' were presented to Grade Eleven pupils; phrasal verbs were taught to one of the Grade Twelve classes and finally, the lesson on vocabulary words 'Best' and 'Favourite' was taught to one of the Grade Eight classes. The comprehension lessons observed were based on the topic 'Child Abuse' and 'Effects of Smoking on the Body' taught to Grade Eleven pupils. The Summary lesson was entitled 'Writing Prose Summary' taught to a Grade 10 class. The composition lesson was taught to a Grade 12 class and was based on the topic 'Writing a Newspaper Article.' The researcher did not come across any lesson presented on either listening or speaking skills. All the lessons observed were on the skills of reading and writing.

Part A: Classroom Events.

Lesson Procedure

Teacher gave the rules for the formation of the three main conditional sentences in tabular form.

Kind of Condition	Tense in Conditional Clause	Tense in main Clause
Open/ likely	Present	Future
Unlikely	Past simple	Conditional
Rejected/ Impossible	Past Perfect	Perfect Condition

Figure 4.2: Illustrations of different form based lessons observed

For the comprehension lessons, the general format was the introduction, silent reading of the text by individual pupils or reading loudly by one member of the class. Thereafter, oral questions were asked to assess the pupils' comprehension of the passage. Comprehension lessons ended with pupils writing an exercise.

Composition lessons were on article and report writing. In both lessons, the teacher defined an 'article' and a 'report'. The teacher gave points on the lay out and asked pupils to copy the points in their exercise books. Lastly, pupils were asked to write an exercise from their course books on the compositions taught.

Participant Organisation

Figure Illustrations of the organisation patterns observed in classrooms

PART B: Communication Features

Teacher Verbal Interaction

In almost all the lessons observed, the teachers consciously used English, the target language. Only one incidence was observed where a teacher used Nyanja, the regional local language of the province. This was basically done to clarify some concepts that were not well understood by the pupils.

With regards to information gap activities, the researcher did not observe any activity as pupils were not engaged in information gap activities. In all the lessons observed, pupils were passive as they only listened attentively to the teacher.

Student Verbal Interaction

Pupils used English, the target language as they responded to the teachers' questions. There was no instance observed where the student initiated discourse. The teacher directed the lessons rigidly. Most speech examples by the students were 'ultra-minimal' or 'minimal' with few examples of sustained speech. The pupils mostly

gave short responses to teachers' questions. During the language lessons, the linguistic form used showed limited restriction. Pupils practiced the linguistic items taught to them by the teacher. The amount of student interaction generally was meager and as a result no attempts were made by other students to incorporate such utterances into the verbal feedback. All the lessons taught were marked by a lack of students requesting information. In terms of giving information, students gave teachers predictable replies in response to the teachers' questions.

Questionnaires

The statistical analysis of the questionnaires administered to all the 41 teachers under study showed that 56.1% teachers frequently engaged students in whole-class discussions and only 2.4% of the respondents stated that they had never done that. The analysis also showed that 4.9% and 36.6% used whole class discussions always and seldom respectively. For group work, a significant number of 70.7% indicated that they used group work seldom and only one respondent (2.4 %) stated that he had never used group work. For individual work, 92.7% stated that they used it always and none of the respondent stated that they have never used it. For role play, 82.9% stated that they had never used role play while 4.9% indicated that they always used role play. Another significant number of 95.1% indicated that respondents had never used co-operative language games in their lessons. Other significant numbers of 90.2%, 85.4%, 63.4%, indicated that the respondents had never engaged pupils in picture strips discussions, rewriting scrambled sentences and dialogues respectively. For debate, 39% indicated that they had seldom used it and 31.7% had never used it. For choral activities, 51.2% stated that they never used it in their teaching while 17.1% indicated that they always used it.

'What are the Factors Hindering Teachers from Implementing CLT?'

During interviews, most teachers acknowledged having used isolated tenets of CLT in their language lessons but they felt that there were many challenges impinging upon the implementation of CLT by the teachers themselves, pupils and the education system as a whole.

Factors Attributed to the Teachers

Inadequate CLT pre-Service Training

All the Forty-one (41) respondents reported that implementing CLT was a very difficult undertaking owing to the fact that teachers did not possess the required knowledge and skills to do that. The argument was generally that colleges and universities did not adequately train them in CLT. Some interviewees stated that they had very little knowledge about CLT and hence they could not implement it. Other respondents stated that they had the knowledge of CLT and its principles but they did not possess the required skills and expertise of putting the premises of CLT into practice. They reported that their pre-service was more theoretical and less practical as far as CLT is concerned. Teacher 4 for instance said:

Lack of Awareness of the syllabi Specifications

Twenty-One (21) of the respondents stated that they were not aware that the English Language Syllabi were guided by CLT Premises.

Lack of Time for Developing CLT Materials and Activities

All the respondents felt that they lacked time for developing materials and activities for CLT. The interviewees from the schools that had Open Learning Classes (OLC) reported that they began teaching at 07:00 hours, break for lunch at 13:00 hours and continue after lunch until 17:00 hours or 17:30 hours in certain cases. This situation according to them made it practically impossible to plan for CLT activities. They stated that by the time they reached home, they were too exhausted to do any preparatory work. In addition to the heavy teaching loads, respondents reported that co-curricular activities such as sports, preventive maintenance, clubs and other responsibilities took up much of their preparatory work.

Poor Enumeration

Fifteen (15) teachers reported that they were not motivated to implement CLT because their salaries were too low. The interviewees stated that teaching English Language was so demanding than any subject in school as marking was very tedious and burdensome. They argued that it would therefore make little sense to venture into yet another tasking undertaking of CLT taking into account the low salaries. They stated that they would willingly implement CLT if they were given extra allowance.

Negative Attitudes towards CLT

Thirteen (13) interviewees cited laziness as yet another factor negatively affecting the implementation of CLT. One of the respondents (teacher 3) stated that the school tries to provide materials in terms of Manila paper and makers but she has no use for such materials because she feels lazy to prepare visual aids. The respondents also stated that in the ten (10) years she has served, she does not remember using any activities such as debates, role plays, dialogues because she feels lazy to sit and plan for such.

Lack of Creativity and Low English Language Proficiency

It was also reported by two interviewees that initiating CLT activities was a very difficult task for teachers because they were not native speakers of the English Language. They stated that planning and initiating CLT activities requires creativity and grammatical competence which they stated was lacking in most of the teachers of English Language. Teacher 9 said:

Factors Attributed to the pupils

Pupils' Negative Attitude towards CLT

Implementation of CLT is also hampered by the negative attitude that pupils display towards it. Twelve (12) teachers pointed out those pupils were used to a culture where they viewed a teacher as an omniscient being or a fountain of knowledge. They assumed that their role as learners in a classroom was to listen passively to a teacher. The respondents pointed out that it was very difficult to engage the learners in CLT activities because they always wanted to listen to a teacher. If a teacher makes the lessons learner centered, the pupils complained and reported such teachers to the school administration. Such teachers were labeled 'lazy' and were never liked by pupils. What pupils generally knew was that a teacher should teach while they sat back and listened to him/her and thought that the only time they could participate in a lesson was when they were asked a question by the teacher. This according to the

respondents made it difficult for a teacher to teach English Language communicatively.

Low levels of English Language Proficiency

The respondents cited low levels of English Language Proficiency as yet another factor making it difficult for teachers to use CLT activities in their lessons. It was reported by Eleven (11) interviewees that it was very difficult to engage pupils in CLT activities such as debates, discussions, role plays, dialogues, communicative games because of low vocabulary levels. It was reported that most pupils shy away because they felt embarrassed to be teased by their fellow pupils every time they uttered ungrammatical sentences. The respondents pointed out that limited command of English language created a problem for students to carry out communicative tasks which often lead to frustrations in the students especially when they were teased. The interviewees stated that CLT activities are always dominated by few pupils that are fluent in English Language. The majority of pupils became spectators during such activities.

Lack of English Language Practice

The interviewees reported that lack of English Language practice was an obstacle to the successful implementation of CLT. Nine (9) respondents stated that pupils only use English Language during English Lessons. When learning other subjects and outside the class, pupils spoke local languages. They stated that the revised school curriculum had even complicated.

Factors Attributed to the Education System

Lack of Teaching and Learning Materials

Twenty Eighty (28) interviewees reported that the schools had inadequate teaching and learning materials to support CLT. The only materials that the respondents mentioned that were provided by the schools were Manila paper, chalk and makers. They attributed this factor to poor funding from the government. Teacher 31 said it was practically impossible to effect CLT because schools lacked resources to procure audio facilities that support the teaching of CLT. Teachers reported that in many instances, they paid from their pockets to print certain materials for the pupils. Teacher 2 said:

VI. Summary of the Findings

From the class observation and questionnaires, it is evident that teachers under study were not inclined to CLT. All the classroom practices revealed that CLT was absent in the English Language lessons. From the study, what dominated was the teaching of structure and was explicitly taught. The explicit teaching of language rules did not occur in the language of use. Learners were not immersed in an authentic input so that the structure of language reflects the functional or communication uses. The structures were introduced as some abstract, predetermined set of grammatical constraints. Beyond grammaticality, learners needed to know which social contexts expect such structures. Learners also needed to acquire aspect of semantic which is only possible if they were immersed in a rich authentic input. Additionally, in both the observations and questionnaires, there was clear evidence that learners were not

given an opportunity to negotiate meaning through engagement in gap tasks such as role plays. The information gap, unpredictability, freedom of choice in both the initiation of the response to discourse, is all seen as authentic communication experiences which were not present in the classrooms.

VII. Disussion Of Findings

Overview

This chapter discusses the findings of the study which sought to establish the factors hindering teachers of English Language from implementing CLT Approach. The discussion is presented according to the objectives of the study which were to; assess teachers' understanding of CLT; explore the extent to which CLT was absent in the English Language lessons and finally, to establish the factors hindering teachers from implementing CLT.

Assess Teachers' Understanding of CLT Approach

Richards (2006) observes that when pressed to give a detailed account of CLT, teachers' explanations will vary widely. Precisely, the study recorded varying responses from the forty-one (41) teachers interviewed. As stated in the foregoing chapter, none of the teachers gave a comprehensive account of CLT that had a sound theoretical base. Thirty-one (31) teachers defined CLT by describing isolated tenets associated with it. Of course these respondents demonstrated that they had scanty ideas that CLT aims at making learners attain communicate competence but what was lacking in their descriptions was a depth understanding of communicative competence. As a result, their definitions gave rise to misconceptions. It was also noted that ten (10) of the respondents could not define CLT. Five (05) of them said that they had forgotten what they had learnt in their pedagogical course at colleges and universities while the other five (5) stated that it was a very difficult task for them.

The studies by Vongxay (2013) Singh and Li (2005), Sato and kleinsasser (1991) showed related results. The study by Vongxay (2013) in particular indicated that teachers in Lao Higher Education Institute in New Zealand had a superficial understanding of CLT. The teachers as reported by Vongxay (2013) defined CLT as interaction among students in the classroom activities. To these teachers, CLT meant speaking and listening tasks and none of them mentioned that it could be in form of writing, reading as well as the involvement of sentence structure which are also element of communicative competence.

Nine (09) teachers understood CLT as an approach that does not involve the teaching of grammar. This misconception was also identified by Thompson (1996) as well as Mapako and Nyota (2012). What is fact is that, CLT places emphasis on meaning but that does not mean structural aspect of language should not be taught. Explicit teaching of language or structures as suggested by Whong (2011) should occur in the context of use and not outside meaningful tasks. As a matter of fact, Canale and Swain (1980) identifies four dimensions of communicative competence and grammatical competence is one of them. It is an essential part of being communicatively competence.

CLT was also regarded by Five (5) respondents as an approach where learners' errors are tolerated. In CLT, fluency is emphasized over more traditional focus on accuracy. Learners are therefore, encouraged to speak without worrying too much about 'correct' forms provided communication is successful (Whong, 2011). This does not mean that errors are entirely ignored. There is selective error correction so that students are not distracted or discouraged. In other words, correction of errors is done when errors lead to a breakdown in communication because "language is created by the individual often through trial and error" (Richards & Rodgers, 1986). What has been discussed is especially true in terms of spoken language production but can also apply to written forms (Whong, 2011).

The study showed that for all the structure lessons observed, a rigid three phase sequence known as Presentation, Practice, and production (P-P-P) cycle was followed. The teacher first presented the new grammar structure by means of giving grammatical rules with examples and this was followed by oral practice as pupils practiced the new structures in a controlled context through question and answer techniques. The teachers asked specific questions based on the structure learnt and the pupils supplied answers accordingly. The lessons ended with the pupils writing exercise where they practiced the learnt structures in a controlled way.

Participant Organisation

The result from the classroom observation showed that teachers organized their classrooms in terms of a teacher to student/class format, focusing on teacher-led, whole class activities. Participant organization was linked to teacher centered activities which encouraged learners to be reactive. Triangulation of the findings by way of questionnaires gave similar results. The statistical analysis showed that 56.1% of teachers frequently engaged students in whole-class activities. For group work, 56.1% indicated that they used group work seldom and for individual work, 92.9% indicated that they used it always while for those that had never used role play were 82.9%. Another significant figure 95.1% was for respondents that stated that they have never used cooperative language games in their lessons.

Other significant number of 92.5%, 92.1% and 65% was for the respondents that stated that they have never engaged pupils in picture strips discussion, rewriting scrambled sentences and dialogues respectively. The above stated findings are against the premises of CLT that promote co-operative rather than individualistic approach to learning (Richards & Rodgers, 1986). CLT does not encourage teacher fronted teaching. It is a learner centred and experience based approach (Whong, 2011). Although there were some indications in the questionnaires that teachers used group work (56.1%), actual classroom practices observed showed contrary results as no single lesson observed had actually used it. Munakaampe (2005) reported similar findings. Teachers displayed roles that were not in Content.

In all the lessons observed, results showed that structure lessons dominated and the focus was the teaching of form rather than function, discourse or sociolinguistics. Admittedly, oral drilling as is the case of some traditional methods (Audio-lingual) did not arise in all the lessons observed. However, similarities in the way oral practice was conducted were observed. The question and answer technique was employed and

was rigidly controlled. The structural elements were not contextualised and learners were at no point given an opportunity to discover rules themselves. Stress was placed on the mastery of grammatical rules that were written on the board for pupils to copy in their exercise book and study. The classroom practice clearly reflected the traditional methods of teaching.

Student Modality

CLT approach is also characterized by an integrated skill approach. A single activity or set of activities in a CLT classroom is likely to make use of all four skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing (Whong, 2011). From the classroom observations, pupils spent their time listening from the teacher's explanation. In the questionnaires, teachers were asked how often they taught these skills interpretively. The statistical results show that 72.5% never did that. The fact that pupils listened more does not mean that listening skills were taught more than the other skills. As earlier indicated, no lesson was specifically taught on listening. The teaching of writing skill dominated all the lessons observed.

Material

Under the banner of CLT, it is expected that authentic materials are used for teaching because they provide exposure to real language, (Richards, 2006). Authentic materials include language based realia such as maps, pictures, symbols, graphs and charts. Different kinds of objects can also be used to support CLT such as models (Richards & Rodgers, 1996). From the classroom observations, the text based course books that were used for summary and comprehension were not authentic but pedagogical in nature.

In many cases, the teachers did not use text books but just gave abstract points especially during composition and structure lessons. It was expected for example, that the composition topic 'Article writing' could have called for the use of authentic materials such as newspapers or magazines. Instead, the teacher just wrote points on how to write an article on the board for pupils to copy. Equally, topics such as contrast could have called for the use of real objects. The possible justification as reported by respondents that teachers are too busy or lazy to plan for CLT activities.

Communicative features (teacher verbal & student verbal interactions)

Generally, from the classroom observations and questionnaires teachers consciously used English, the target language. The teaching in all the classes was not communicative in nature and as such pupils were not engaged in information gap activities. Equally, pupils were passive as they only listened attentively to the teacher. The pupils' speech was ultra-minimal or minimal in all the lessons observed. Pupils only gave short responses to the teachers' questions as they were not engaged in communicative activities.

Establishing Factors Hindering Teachers of English Language from Implementing CLT Approach

Through interviews with the teachers under study, several factors were identified as a hindrance to the implementation of CLT. The first category of factors was attributed to the teachers and included factors such as inadequate pre-service training, few

opportunities for re-training in CLT, lack of awareness of the syllabus specifications, lack of time for CLT planning, poor enumeration, lack of commitment to CLT, lack of creativity and low English Language proficiency. The second category of the factors were attributed to the pupils and included factors such as pupils' negative attitude towards CLT, low levels of English Language proficiency and lack of English Language practice. In the third category, the interviewees stated that lack of teaching and learning materials had a bearing on the implementation of CLT. They also stated that large classes, structural exams, limited time allocation on the time table were a hindrance to the teaching of CLT. A lack of convenient classrooms for CLT was yet another factor identified.

Factors Attributed to the Teachers

In adequate pre-service Training in CLT

Kendall (1989) observed that resistance to change has its origin in the participant's early experiences and training. The failure or success of an innovation has so much on the training experiences of the teachers. In this regard, the responses from all the teachers showed that the training they underwent did not prepare them for the teaching of CLT. The argument was that training was more theoretical than practical and the time spent on CLT was limited. On average, the respondents stated that CLT was discussed in just one-hour lecture which was not adequate to prepare them for classroom practice. The findings from other scholars showed related results.

For example, Chang (2010) and Weimann (1996) reported that Taiwanese college of Education teachers and teachers at Ciskeians Schools acknowledged having learnt the approach during their training but they indicated that they lacked the practical aspect of it. The respondents argued that didactics course and the model presented to them by College lecturers failed to provide sufficient understanding of, and practice in CLT. Similarly, Vongxay (2013) reported that most of the teachers in his research indicated that in order to adopt CLT in their classes, they needed to be retrained to update their skills to facilitate and create communicative activities in their classrooms.

5.8. Few Opportunities for Re-training in CLT.

Related to the above stated matter is the fact that teachers are not given any opportunities for retraining in CLT. It was established that schools conduct C.P.D Meetings regularly and also that the Languages Teachers' Association of Zambia (LATAZ) organizes Conferences annually for its members but at no time was CLT holistically discussed. Of course, the respondents acknowledged that certain tenets of CLT such as the use of group work and making the lessons learner centred were discussed but they stated that there was no time when these principles were linked to CLT. They stated that the tenets are merely looked at as good practices in education and were not in any way linked to CLT. What came out was basically that C.P.D Meetings and English Language Conferences were dominated by structural topics, summary and compositions. The focus of CPD meetings as reported were the exam items and issues of pedagogy were never discussed.

Lack of Awareness of the syllabi specifications

The syllabi serve several important purposes and the most basic of them is to communicate the instructors course design (goals, organization, policies,

expectations, requirements) to students (Parkes & Harris, 2002). It is expected that in a given program, students should have an in depth understanding of the syllabi specifications. It is however not the case in this study. The findings showed that 40% of the respondents were not aware that the English Language Syllabi were guided by CLT premises. When asked to state what approach they were using, the respondents were at a loss.

All they said was that they just followed the topics as outlined in the course book. What was even more surprising was that these respondents had the syllabi in their teaching files but could not actually read and interpret it. This kind of attitude was worrisome and it raises concerns over the roles of H.O. Ds and standard officers. It certainly gives an impression that monitoring of the school is not as effective as expected. From the interviews with some H.O. Ds, it appears they are also moving at the same wave length as the teachers in their departments. This kind of situation most likely could be stemming from the earlier discussed factor of training.

Lack of time for Developing CLT materials and Activities

Fifty percent (50%) of the respondents identified lack of time for preparation as a drawback in the implementation of CLT. The teachers reported that they had little time for planning because of teaching overloads and in many cases; they were engaged in the supervision of Co-curricular activities and many administrative activities. What came out strongly was that CLT was too demanding unlike traditional methods of teaching. Mareva and Mapako (2011) regarded this view as a misconception. These researchers agreed to the fact that CLT teachers had to be resourceful but denied the understanding that CLT places too much demands on the teachers. Citing Richard and Rodgers (1995), they argued that CLT weans the teacher from the rigours of taking center stage in the language learning classrooms. and research and such responsibilities cannot be down played. In fact, the idea of resourcefulness in CLT well acknowledged by Mareva and Mapato (2012) entails a lot of work for the teacher than portrayed.

Poor Enumeration

The respondents cited poor enumeration as one of the factors negatively affecting the implementation of CLT. The teachers reported that they were not motivated to implement CLT because their salaries were too low and did not match the demands placed upon them by CLT. The four respondents (33%) argued that they could willingly implement CLT if they were given a pay rise. The impression created was that the approaches and methods they were using then were less demanding and in a way equaled their income.

The remarks by the respondents are similar to the observation made by Hurst (1981) that it would appear futile to ask teachers to change practices or to support and promote reforms when the ratio of fields to input is not better than their existing practices. His observation was basically that teachers involved in planned education change are made to work much harder for little visible pay-off. This according to him negatively affected the implementation of an innovation. Precisely, the observation by Hurst (1987) was the bone of contention as respondents strongly felt that a shift to CLT should call for a pay rise.

Negative Attitudes toward CLT

Two respondents (17%) cited laziness as yet another factor negatively affecting the implementation of CLT. One of the two respondents categorically stated that even when she was provided with teaching and learning materials, she found it very difficult to sit and plan for CLT because she felt lazy. This kind of an attitude can have several interpretations. One of it is probably that the teachers in question view the outcomes of CLT as irrelevant and has no impact on the final exams.

Lack of Creativity and Low English Language Proficiency

Ellis argues that the successful adoption of CLT into EFL classrooms depends on the teachers English Language proficiency among other factors. This statement is true to the findings recorded in this study were some respondents reported that planning and initiating CLT activities required a lot of creativity and grammatical competence which they said was lacking in most of them because they were not native speakers of the language. Similar findings were reported by Li (1998) that Chinese skills of reading and writing were inadequate to enable them conduct communicative activities in their classroom. Weimann (1996) found similar results.

The researcher expected a difficult outcome owing to the fact that English Language has been used as a medium of instruction way back from colonial era (Kashoki, 1989). It is evident by this study that despite using English Language for some time now, the desired proficiency in English Language has not been attained by most teachers.

Factors Attributed to the pupils

Pupils Negative Attitude toward CLT

The study reviewed that pupils displayed a negative attitude towards CLT practices of child centered learning. The respondents stated that it was difficult to engage the learners in CLT activities because of their traditions that looks at a teacher as a conveyer of knowledge. This study is similar to the research findings by Chang (2010) were pupils in Taiwan were reported to be quiet and only waited for the teachers call to answer questions. Similar findings were reported by Chowdhry (2010) in Bangladesh that students expected teachers to be authority figures and the teaching methods to conform to the tradition 'lack step' teacher centred approach. Weimann (1996) also reported that teachers in Ciskeians Schools were reluctant to implement CLT because of the student's culture which looks at a teacher as a fountain of knowledge.

Low levels of English Language Proficiency

Some respondents reported low proficiency in English Language by the pupils as a hindrance to the implementation of CLT activities such as debates, discussions role plays and dialogues. The findings were that it was difficult to engage pupils in communicative activities because they lacked the oral competence. It was also stated that pupils generally shy away from such activities because they feel embarrassed every time they uttered ungrammatical sentences. The findings are similar to those obtained by Chang (2010), Li (1998) and Weimann (1996).

However, further research is required so that the matter is comprehensively understood.

Lack of English Language practice

As stated in the discussion above, nine respondents reported that pupils used English Language during English Lessons only. When learning other subjects and indeed during play time, pupils spoke in their local languages. The teachers attributed the use of local languages to the revised.

Factors Attributed to the Education System

Lack of Teaching and Learning Materials

Lack of teaching resources was identified to be a factor hindering the implementation of CLT. Twenty-Eight (28) respondents reported that the schools were poorly funded and as a result, they were unable to buy the teaching and learning materials. The only materials that most of the schools stated had were course books, chalk and in certain cases Manila paper.

As stated by Rao (2002), most education institutions do not have enough financial resources required to provide the audiovisual equipment, photocopiers and other facilities that are required to support the dynamic teaching associated with CLT. The findings are similar to those recorded by Mareva and Nyota (2011) in a study of English Language teaching in Masvingo urban and peri-urban secondary Schools. Analysis showed that teachers relied heavily on the text books as a source of material and the chalk board as a learning aid. They stated that their findings are in support of Structural Approach and not CLT which advocates the use of realia. Similar findings were also reported by Incey and Incey (2009).

Large classes

The large size of classes was identified to be a hindrance to the implementation of CLT by Twenty-three respondents (23). It was reviewed that collaborative learning which is encouraged in CLT is difficult to implement because of the numbers of pupils that were estimated at 75% per class on average. The difficulties that were faced because of the large classes included management and disciplinary issues. Teachers stated that no meaningful learning took place in such classes and very few learners benefited ultimately from collaborative learning.

Structural Exams

Structural and grammar oriented examinations were reported to be a setback in the implementation of CLT. The interviewee pointed out that they found it irrelevant and a waste of time to teach CLT because the national examinations are structural in nature. What was reported was that the skills of listening and speaking were not examined and as such no attention is given to the teaching of these skills.

Limited Time Allocation on the Time Table

Mareva and Nyota (2011) established during their research that most of the teachers under study rejected group work as a central technique because it was perceived to take much of teaching time. In a way, the findings by these researchers are similar to those established by this research. The teachers reported that English Language had

the maximum of 80 minutes for a double period which according to them was inadequate for CLT activities. Their experiences were that they failed to finish communicative activities such as debate in 80 minutes. During classroom observations, the researcher witnessed instances where teachers failed to finish composition and comprehension lessons in 80 minutes. Of course, the lesson as earlier stated were not communicative in nature. But it could be stated here that this was common with non-communicative lessons observed as well.

Classes not convenient for CLT

Earthman (2002), reporting on California revealed that comfortable classroom temperature and smaller classes enhance teachers' effective opportunities for students to receive more individual attention ask more questions, participate more fully in discussions, reduce discipline problems and perform better than students in substandard buildings by several percentages. In the same vein, four (4) respondents all from one school reported that their classrooms were not convenient for CLT. The respondents reported that their classrooms had no electricity making it so difficult for them to use audio-visual aids. The classes were also reported to have prevented them from using collaborative learning because they were too small and poorly ventilated such that teachers were forced to teach while standing by the window or by the door side.

Summary

The discussion shows that teachers' understanding of CLT was meager. The study also revealed that to a very large extent CLT was absent in the English Language lessons and several factors were identified to impinge upon the successful implementation of CLT.

VIII. Conclusion And Recommendations

This chapter concludes the study and also makes recommendations based on the findings of the study.

Conclusion

CLT can be understood if it is looked at as a set of principles about the goals of language teaching, how learners learn a language, the kind of classroom activities that best facilitate learning, and the roles of teachers and learners in the classroom (Richards, 2006). Basing on this explanation, the results of the first objective which aimed at assessing teachers understanding of CLT reviewed that none of the teachers under study could give a detailed account of CLT Approach. However, the study showed that thirty-one respondents (75.6%) had misconceptions about CLT. Generally, the misconceptions helmed from the semantic understanding that CLT is all about teaching oral communication skills and does not involve the teaching of grammar. The study also showed that Ten (24.3%) of the respondents had difficulties in defining CLT and therefore they either kept quiet or stated that they had forgotten what they had learnt during training.

The second objective of the study was to establish the extent to which CLT was used in English Language lessons. The results obtained through questionnaires and

classroom observations showed that teachers under study were not in any way inclined to CLT Approach. The classrooms were organized around teacher-centered, teacher-led, whole class pedagogical activities without any noticeable form of communicative activities and CLT instructional procedure. Pupils were never given any opportunity to initiate discourse and therefore not playing any role in the negotiation and creation of learning opportunities. The language skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing were never taught in an integrative way. More so, of all the lessons observed, only reading and writing skills were taught. What dominated was the explicit teaching of structures. Learners were not immersed in an authentic input so that the structure of language reflected the functional or communicative uses.

Recommendations

1. The Ministry of General Education should begin conducting in-service training so that teachers who may not be aware of CLT are sensitized on the approach in vogue. The teachers who may be aware of CLT also need to be sensitized also so that they get committed to the approach and implement it correctly.
2. The trainers of English Language teachers should endeavor to prepare student teachers adequately not only theoretically but also practically by giving them frequent opportunities for exposure to CLT approach during their period of training.
3. There should be increased funding to schools and the department of literature and languages in particular so that materials and equipment may be procured.
4. The monitoring of schools by standards officers should be effectively done so that teachers are guided on the pedagogical requirements of the syllabus.
5. The government of the Republic of Zambia should consider building more schools or expanding already existing schools so that they control over enrolment.

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